

DAMAGE CHARACTERIZATION OF A THIN PLATE MADE OF ABS UNDER UNIAXIAL SOLICITATION

H. Farid^{1,2*}, F. Erchiqui¹, M. Elghorba², K. Elhad², F. Slaoui Hasnaoui¹, H. Ezzaidi³

¹ Laboratory of Bioplastics and Nanotechnology, University of Québec in Abitibi-Témiscamingue, Québec, Canada,

² Laboratory of Mechanical Control and Characterization of Structures and Materials, National Highest School of Electricity and Mechanics, Casablanca, Morocco,

³ Research Group for Renewable Energy and the Impact of Nordic Climate, Université du Québec A Chitoutimi, 555 Boulevard de l'Université, Chicoutimi, Québec G7H 2B1, Canada

* Corresponding author (hicham.farid@uqat.ca)

Keywords: *Mechanical damage, the damage theory, uniaxial characterization, ABS.*

Abstract

We assist to a remarkable rise of the use of polymers in many industrial fields. Even if they are widely used in both high performance or ordinary products, their versatility makes them very necessary for new applications, and it requires a thorough understanding of their physical, chemical, rheological and mechanical properties. Determining the mechanical behavior of these materials becomes very necessary either during processing or during operation. In this work, we focus on the characterization of a notched flat plate ABS under uniaxial stress. Unified theory of damage is considered to characterize and quantify the damage. Our crucial goal is the study of the stress concentration factor, and a contribution to the determination of the damage degree of notched structures.

Introduction

Many engineering studies show that whatever the material (metal, polymers, composites, or wood), in spite of their various microstructures and physical properties, the qualitative mechanical behavior they exhibit is

substantially identical. These include an elastic behavior, a yield stress, certain plasticity or irreversible deformation, more or less important deformation anisotropy, a hysteresis ring with damage by monotonic or cyclic loading, and a crack initiation under static or dynamic loading [1].

Additionally, they exhibit many levels of imperfections, due to processing, post processing handling such as transportation and storage. Such imperfections include knit lines, flaws, vacuum or inclusions which make polymer-based structures heterogeneous to a certain degree. The consequences of the presence of knit lines for example in such materials on the mechanical properties are discussed by Criens and Moslé [2]. Due to the presence of crazes, scratches, cracks and other imperfections, the mechanical properties of real polymeric materials are not as good as they theoretically could be [3].

Damage mechanics aims at modeling these phenomena at the level of structures calculations. The purpose of this approach being to build behavior models which once included

in a calculation code, could simulate the fracture and, more generally, to estimate the state of damages in a structure according to one or many ultimate states [4].

Modeling the structural behavior of polymers has been the subject of a range of researches. In this regard, several authors have addressed the problem of rheological behavior [5], forming and processing modeling [6], and the behavior during the failure process [7].

This work is a contribution to the study of the failure mechanism of a flat plate made by ABS (Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene). Initially, the structural behavior of a smooth plate has been studied, in aim to study and reveal the mechanical characteristic under uniaxial solicitation tensile test, followed by a series of tests conducted on notched flat plates, the notch effect will be discussed and highlighted through experimental results. Finally, through the application of the stress concentration factor criteria [8], and the Unified Damage Theory [9], the damage evolution in the ABS material is investigated.

Theory

Generally, damage decreases the stiffness and resistance of materials. For a given stress state, the deformations are all larger than the damage is high. Hence the importance of coupled calculations, which calculates simultaneously stress, strain and damage in mechanical properties evolution problems.

The main aim of damage theories is to define a Damage parameter which translates the damage state of the structure. However, it remains a delicate problem since nothing (or almost nothing!) distinguishes a damaged volume element of a virgin (blank) volume element macroscopically. It is then necessary to imagine an internal variable representing the state of deterioration of the material.

Several models are proposed for damage modeling in structural calculation. The most responded model is the Minner model of damage [10], [11], however it remains limited in

its linear method of description of the cumulative damage progress, which does not accurately reflect the state of the deterioration of the structure. Other proposed approaches have tried to adjust this model to a more adequate damage presentation; they include the models of Miller [12] and Chaboche [13]...

In order to address the various points omitted by the theoretical damage models, Bui-Quoc [9] proposed a model that involves several loading parameters. The Unified Theory has thus been developed in this context, to define damage parameter which is the internal variable that describe the damage state of the structure in terms of the a life fraction $D = f(\beta)$, the fraction of life depends on solicitation conditions (for example the number of cycle for dynamics loading, notch dimension for static tensile loading, temperature conditioning...).

In this respect, the endurance limit is defined as the stress level below which there is no damage, the part supports an infinite number of cycles in fatigue tests for example, or its resistance reach the highest level for a notched static test specimen. The rate of reduction of the endurance limit to the number of applied fatigue cycles for a dynamic solicitation test was suggested as follows:

$$\frac{d\gamma_\varepsilon}{dn} = -\frac{1}{K} \gamma^b (\gamma - \gamma_{\varepsilon r})^2 \quad (1)$$

Where the various terms are successively:

$\gamma_\varepsilon = \sigma_\varepsilon / \sigma_0$	Non-dimensional endurance limit
$\gamma = \sigma / \sigma_0$	Non-dimensional cyclic stress
$\gamma_{\varepsilon r} = \sigma_{\varepsilon r} / \sigma_0$	Instantaneous non-dimensional endurance limit
σ_0	Endurance limit of the virgin material
σ	Applied stress level
K and b	Material constants

n Number of applied fatigue cycles

With boundary conditions:

- i. $n = 0$ $\gamma_{er} = 1$
- ii. $n = N_f$
 $\gamma_{er} = (\sigma/\sigma_u)^m$

Where N_f is the number of cycles to failure for a fatigue test; for our study, it represents the critical diameter of the hole, m is an empirical material constant superior to one.

$$N_f = \frac{K}{\gamma^b} \left[\frac{1}{\gamma - 1} - \frac{1}{\gamma - (\gamma/\gamma_u)^m} \right] \quad (2)$$

With

$$\gamma_u = \sigma_u/\sigma_0$$

This equation determines the relationship between stress and applied number of cycles. The normalized damage is defined by:

$$D = \frac{1 - \gamma_{er}}{1 - \gamma_e} \quad (3)$$

With

$$\gamma_e = \sigma_e/\sigma_0$$

By setting $\beta = n/N_f$ this theory leads to the following equation:

$$D = \frac{1}{\beta + (1 - \beta) \left[\frac{\gamma - (\gamma/\gamma_u)^m}{\gamma - 1} \right]} \quad (4)$$

For the damage quantification in the material, we used the damage variable for each life fraction, so by analogy with theory shown above, the life fraction of our study represents the relationship between the hole diameter progression and its critical value, which is the value of the larger hole diameter. Based on the earlier presented theories, we chose the law of damages given by the unified theory. The mean advantage of this theory relative to other

approaches is to directly link the damage progress of the material to the variation of the ultimate residual limit, thus directly connecting the material's damage to its characteristics.

The damage variable can thus be defined as:

$$D = \frac{1 - \frac{\sigma_{ur}}{\sigma_u}}{1 - \frac{\sigma_l}{\sigma_u}} \quad (5)$$

Where

σ_{ur} is the ultimate residual stress

σ_u is the ultimate limit,

σ_l is the stress limit

Experimental

A series of tests was carried on for the characterization of material damage, on two series of rectangular specimens of ABS (Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene), based on the guidelines prescribed by the ASTM D 882-02 [14] and ASTM D5766M [15]. The first series consisted of rectangular smooth specimens (without hole) to characterize the material and the second series consisted of rectangular specimens with holes of 1 mm to 7 mm diameters. The first series was used as the reference, and the second to monitor and highlight the influence of the hole size on the specimen behaviour. All the experimental series was conducted under controlled displacement. Elongations were determined using the displacement sensor crosshead incorporated in the machine. Figure 1 below shows the set-up for the tensile test.

Figure 1. Experimental set-up : A test specimen held by the sample holder of the tensile testing machine (left), and dimensions of the test specimen (right).

Results

In the notched specimen, a stress concentration phenomenon near the hole takes place, and the response of the structure to the applied effort is affected depending on the hole diameter, we talk here on a notch effect.

Figure 2 shows the stress versus strain curves for the specimens with holes. As the tests proceed, these curves show a striking decreasing pace, and the gap between the values.

Figure 2. Evolution of the stress-strain curves for uniaxial tensile tests on rectangular test specimens with 1mm to 7mm hole diameters, according to ASTM D 882-02 two and ASTM D5766M

In fact, these curves show a remarkable degradation of the mechanical properties of the material with an increase in hole diameter; these properties include the elastic stress, ultimate stress, the failure stress and the elongation. We observe an area of stress stabilization, and a

high elongation (maximum elongation). Additionally, rupture is often preceded by local yielding followed by an abrupt failure.

The mechanical characteristics are affected due to the notch effect; the characteristics decrease as long as the notch diameter increases. Figures 3 shows the evolution of the ultimate stress the with hole diameter:

Figure 3. Ultimate stress evolution with hole diameters

Figure 4. Stiffness evolution with hole diameters

As already mentioned above, a decrease in the ultimate stress (maximum stress value reached in the tensile test) with hole diameters was observed.

The right branch of the stress-strain curve present the elastic response of the specimen, this branch allows the calculation of the *Young Modulus*. However, with the existence of the hole, we talk more about *Stiffness* for notched specimens' more than *Young modulus* for smooth specimens. The stiffness determines then the elastic response limits for notched structures. Figure 4 shows a significant rise in stiffness until values closer to those given by smooth specimens which represent the Young's modulus.

As discussed above, the existence of notch affect the mechanical characteristics of the material, the evolution of its size has also remarkable influence on those properties. Figure 5 shows a schematical evolution of the ultimate dimensionless stress versus dimensionless hole diameter.

The ultimate dimensionless stress was obtained by dimensionlessness of the ultimate residual stress (the residual ultimate stress is given as the ultimate value of stress reached by a sane specimen in a simple tensile test, for our study, its value is $\sigma_{ur} = 34 \text{ MPa}$) by the ultimate stress level obtained for each hole diameter. The same for the dimensionless hole diameter which was obtained by dimensionlessness of the hole diameter by the critical hole diameter (the larger value of the hole diameter above which the structure no longer support any effort).

Figure 5. Evolution of the ultimate dimensionless stress versus the dimensionless hole diameter

Figure 5 illustrates the ultimate dimensionless stress evolution versus the dimensionless hole diameter; the curve shows a decrease of the material ultimate stress while the dimensionless hole increases. The intersection with the interval limit allows us to determine a stress limit below which we estimate that the damage occurred to the material remains acceptable, this stress limit has as value $\sigma_1 = 24.82 \text{ MPa}$.

Figure 6 reports the variation of the resistance loss with the dimensionless diameter of the holes. It shows that the resistance loss is remarkable and it becomes increasingly important when approaching the critical value of the default already prescribed.

The aim of this representation is to show the resistance loss of the material due to the damage accumulation, this damage itself is due to the notch and its evolution in the structure.

Fatigue behaviour of the material, as characterized through its endurance limit, allows us to determine the endurance limit that will be used later for the quantification of the material damage. The endurance limit was determines for the ABS smooth samples, through fatigue test, and takes as value $\sigma_0 = 18 \text{ MPa}$ [16].

Figure 6. The resistance loss in static tension

Both curves of Figure 6 have the same shape like the one giving the variation of the ultimate limit. Both show a resistance decrement while the dimensionless hole diameter keep increasing. The intersection between the later curve and the boundary of the interval of study gives a value $\sigma_0^* = 7.2 \text{ MPa}$ which is considered the safe endurance limit value below which no fatigue failure will occur.

Damage in the ABS notched plates

Figure 7. Evolution of the damage versus the fraction of life

For quantifying the damage occurred into the notched structure, we propose a damage variable based on presentation demonstrated above in equation (5). The proposition of this variable was taken by analogy with cumulative damage theory proposed by Gatts [17] and retaked by Bui-Quoc [9]. The proposed approach present the damage evolution into a notched structure, and link the damage state of the material to an intrinsic property which is its residual stress.

The damage on the notched samples with the non-dimensional hole diameters is shown in the figure 7. The damage nearly follows a linear variation. At the initiation, the damage is negligible ($D \approx 0$) for a smooth flat plate. As the hole size increases, the damage accelerates a maximum value of 0.9 is reached where failure occurred. The initiation area is characterized by the highest mechanical characteristics for the materials, while the point of failure is marked by their remarkable degradation.

Stress concentration in the notched ABS plates

The concept of a stress concentration factor is often employed by designers to account for the increase of stress at a concentration point, the nominal stress being multiplied by a stress concentration factor to obtain and estimate of the local stress at the point.

Generally, Stress concentration is a phenomenon of a local stress increasing in an area which contains geometric modifications [18]. It appears in a discontinuity of a part or a structure for example with the presence of a notch after machining. The area of stress concentration is most often the site of crack initiation. In many cases, particularly in which the stress is highly localized, a mathematical analysis proves difficult or impracticable. Then, experimental or mechanical methods of stress analysis are used.

The vicinity of the incident form is characterized by a heterogeneous stress distribution leading to the stress concentration, thus stress concentration factor is defined as “the quotient of the maximal applied stress to the corresponding nominal stress” [19]:

$$K_t = \frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_{nom}} \quad (6)$$

The severity of the stress concentration depends on both the notch geometry and the notch configuration. Stress concentration is an important factor to be considered during every structural design, as issues such as sudden break can be avoided either by reducing or by avoiding it [20].

The stress concentration factor variation relative to the specimen ratio hole diameter to width is shown in the figure 8.

Figure 8. Evolution of the stress concentration factor with the hole diameter based on the ratio D/W for notched plate

The stress concentration factor decreases with the ratio D/W. This means that stress concentration increases with a reduction of D/W. Additionally, this concentration tends

towards stability when the ratio D/W increases, thus the maximum stress is equal to the nominal stress, and the large size of the defect has no effect on this ratio.

Conclusion

The objective of this work was to characterize the damage behavior of a thermoplastic flat plate. It found that the uniaxial tensile test was the most practical approach and the closest representation of the real state of deformation during the real solicitation. This technique was used to describe the damage developed in the material. The unified damage theory was used in the aim to give a more complete damage model that can more faithfully describe the state of the material. This approach was applied to several materials; however the results reported in this article are only based on ABS.

The results obtained have highlighted the applicability of the reported damage approach. The proposed approach involves the use of the intrinsic parameters of the material, thus a rigorous description of the damage state of the materials. These preliminary studies are essential steps towards the full achievement of our mid-term goals of performing and developing tools for modeling and simulating of thermoplastic forming processes.

References

- [1] Sanchez-Santana U., Comportement dynamique des matériaux et structures après sollicitation en fatigue. Thèse de doctorat, Université des sciences et technologies de Lille, 2007.
- [2] Criens R.M. and Moslé H.G., Faillure of plastics, edited by W. Brostow and R.D. Corneliunssen Hauser, 1986.
- [3] Brostow W., Kubàt J. and Kubàt M., Physical properties of polymers handbook, Chapter 23: Mechanical properties, American Institute of physics, James E. Mark editor, 1996.
- [4] Lemaitre J. and Chaboche J.L., Aspect phénoménologique de la rupture par

- endommagement, journal de la mécanique appliquée, Vol 2, 1978.
- [5] Shia-Chung C., Rheological behavior of PS polymer melt under ultra-high speed injection molding, Polymer Testing Journal, Volume 31, Issue 7, October 2012.
- [6] Erchiqui F., Ozdemir Z., Souli M., Ezzaidi H., Dituba-Ngoma G., Neural networks approach for characterization of viscoelastic polymers, volume 89, Issue 5, October 2011.
- [7] Figueredo R., Cherouat A., Une nouvelle approche dans la prise en compte de la déformation permanente et volumique induite par l'endommagement dans la mise en forme des structures caoutchoutiques, 19^{ème} Congrès Français de Mécanique, Marseille 2009.
- [8] Davis J.R., Tensile testing second edition, ASM International, The material information society 2004.
- [9] Bui-Quoc T., Dubuc J., Bazergui A., Biron A., Cumulative fatigue damage under stress-controlled conditions, Journal of Basic Engineering, Transactions of the ASME, 1971.
- [10] Miner M., Cumulative damage in fatigue, Journal of Applied Mechanics, Volume 12, 1945.
- [11] Jardin A., Leblond J.B., Berghezan D., Par-delà la loi de Miner pour la modélisation de la fatigue des élastomères : théorie et expérimentation, 19^{ème} Congrès Français de Mécanique, Marseille 2009.
- [12] Miller K.J., Zachariah K.P, Cumulative damage fatigue crack initiation and state I propagation, Journal of Strain Analysis, 1977.
- [13] Lemaitre J, Chaboche J.L, Mechanics of Solid Materials, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1990.
- [14] D 882-02 ASTM Standard test method for tensile properties of thin plastic sheeting.
- [15] D 5766 M ASTM Standard test method for open hole tensile strength of polymer matrix composite laminates.
- [16] E606 / E606M - 12 ASTM Standard Test Method for Strain-Controlled Fatigue Testing.
- [17] Gatts R., Application of cumulative damage concept to fatigue, ASTM Transactions, Journal of basic engineering, Volume 83, 1961.
- [18] Lemaignan C., La Rupture des matériaux, EDP Sciences 2003.
- [19] Boresi A.P., Sidebottom O.M., Advanced mechanics of materials 4th edition, John Wiley and sons 1985.
- [20] Lemaitre J, Chaboche J.L, Mécanique des matériaux solides 3^{ème} édition, Edition Dunod 2009.